

Title: Human Capital Considerations for Blockchain Implementation

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The Blockchain Academy Inc. is a global training company. Delivering programs on bitcoin, blockchain protocols, cryptocurrencies and smart contracts. We a focus on two channels, Senior Management/Stakeholders and Developers. As part of our live & online training, we deeply integrate technology into our training curriculum which are used by corporations and universities.

Bryant leads a team of instructors and programmers which use 'technology' to enable learning on a global scale. The Blockchain Academy Inc. maintains offices in New York&New Jersey.

INTRODUCTION:

As more and more organizations go beyond proof of concept and begin to pilot and roll out blockchain projects, there will be a need for highly skilled blockchain practitioners, from developers to architects and in-house experts. This session will explore the human capital requirements including training and education, staffing and recruitment, culture management and change.

AIM:

To raise awareness of the need for companies to manage their human capital resources for enterprise deployment of blockchain technology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

n/a

RESULTS:

n/a

CONCLUSIONS:

Companies need to manage the coming talent needs that are going to impact them with the deployment of blockchain. Specifically dealing with:

- *Blockchain Training & Development*
- *Recruitment & HR*
- *Encouraging diversity in Blockchain*

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, Human Capital, Implementation, Technology

BIOGRAPHY:

Bryant Nielson is the Founder and CEO of The Blockchain Academy.

The Blockchain Academy offers both live and online video based programs, delivered by industry experts, on the role of blockchain, its impact on central banks, financial institutions, trade finance, settlement, smart contracts, IP as well as blockchain developer education. Bryant has written extensively about Blockchain and is a regular speaker at blockchain conferences globally. He has delivered talks at numerous conferences in New York, Chicago, London, Mexico City, Moscow and Dubai. He currently delivers courses on Blockchain Essentials as well as Blockchain for Lawyers. He is also the host of a blockchain podcast: Blockchain360.